

Water quality analyses in the Upper Ntombe River

Jeff W. Morris

(jeffwmorris@gmail.com)

Executive Summary

This report evaluates the water quality of the Sibandlu and Upper Ntombe Rivers within the KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment (KPE). Analysis of 12 samples collected during low-flow (June 2025) and record-high-flow (January 2026) periods reveals a catchment in excellent ecological health, characterised by highly stable pH (7.0–7.4) and low baseline mineralisation.

Principal component analysis (PCA) identified three primary drivers of water quality: mineralisation (PC1), seasonal shifts in alkalinity (PC2), and anthropogenic impact (PC3). While both rivers are remarkably clean by national standards, the Ntombe River exhibits a consistently higher and more persistent "pollution fingerprint" (elevated *E. coli* and Nitrates) compared to the Sibandlu River. This difference is attributed to the presence of irrigated cultivation in the Ntombe catchment, whereas the Sibandlu remains undeveloped. The study confirms that while rainfall volume significantly dilutes mineral concentrations, the Ntombe River's pollution sources remain stable regardless of flow, whereas the Sibandlu River's microbial profile is more flow-dependent and dynamic.

Keywords

Anthropogenic Impact
Catchment Management
E. coli Water Testing
Ecological Health Assessment
Environmental PCA Analysis
Free-flowing Rivers South Africa
High-flow vs Low-flow Hydrology
KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment (KPE)
Mpumalanga Water Quality
Multivariate Statistical Analysis
Ntombe River
Phongola River
Principal Component Analysis (PCA)
River Mineralisation Gradient
Sibandlu River
Upper Ntombe Catchment
Water Chemistry Baseline

Introduction

It is generally recognised that the water flowing from the KwaMandlangampisi mountains is very clean, with low levels of pollution and few impurities. This project set out to quantify this understanding as of today. As well as creating a baseline for monitoring in future, can differences in quality between the time of year and between water from the two main sources be quantified?

The KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment (KPE) is situated in Mpumalanga, about 20km from the village of Lüneburg, which is across the border in KwaZulu-Natal. The KPE covers approximately 30,000ha. The first phase of the protected environment declaration was gazetted in 2010 and has remained in effect since. The land is privately owned, except for the Paardeplaas Nature Reserve, which is owned by the Mpumalanga Tourism and Parks Authority (MTPA). Details are available in the current Management Plan (MTPA 2025). Commercial farming activities are the order of the day with free-range livestock (cattle and sheep), some commercial forestry, and irrigated cash-crop cultivation in the area.

In 2025, an initiative began to document the environment and biodiversity of the KPE. This report on the water quality of two of the main rivers sourced in the KPE is one such outcome. The KPE is rich in terms of hydrological resources. A great many tributary rivers and wetlands regulate the flow of water from this area. Three major river systems (quaternary catchments W42A, B, and C, and W51A), including the Phongola River and its downstream irrigation requirements, are fed by this area. Furthermore, the Mpumalanga Biodiversity Sector Plan Handbook (2014) identified the area encompassing the KPE as highly important for its hydrological and ecological services. The Ntombe River, the main subject of this report, is the only one in Mpumalanga and one of thirteen in South Africa classified as a flagship free-flowing river by the Water Research Commission (2011).

Methods

In June 2025, at a time of low water flow, six water samples were collected from tributaries of the Phongola River. Four were from the Sibandlu sub-catchment and two from the Ntombe sub-catchment (the Low-flow samples) (Figure 1). Another six samples were collected in January 2026 during a period of strong river flow (High-flow). One sample from a low-flow period was provided by the Impala Water Users Association (IWUA), bringing the total to 13 samples.

The calendar year 2025 was an exceptional one for rainfall. The long-term average for a recording station in the area from 1999 to 2024 was 1282mm. The total for 2025 was 2234mm, with 1800mm falling in the last six months of the year. This was by far the highest recorded annual rainfall over the period, with the second highest in 2006 (1858mm). The low-flow samples were collected at the end of a dry period; only 434mm had been recorded in the previous six months. The high-flow samples were collected after this exceptionally heavy rainfall over the previous few months. Runoff at low flow was minimal, whereas heavy rainfall ensured that surface runoff was high when the high-flow samples were collected. In fact, flooding of tracks prevented the repeat collection of a sample at Node 5. The corresponding sample was taken at Node 4 instead.

The river system is described in terms of Nodes and river stretches between Nodes (Figure 1). The Ntombe River enters the KPE upstream of Node 1. From there, it flows through Node 2 and exits the KPE beyond Node 9. One sample was collected downstream (Node 3), where the IWUA sample (P2) was also collected. Three of the many sources of the Sibandlu River were sampled (Nodes 4, 5 and 6). The confluence of

Nodes 4 and 5 is upstream of Node 7. From Node 7, the river flows through Node 10 and Node 8 before reaching the confluence with the Ntombe River at Node 9. Node 6 joins the Sibundlu River at Node 10.

Details of the samples are given in Table 1. WaterLab in Pretoria analysed 21 variables on each of the first 12 samples, as shown in Table 2. The IWUA sample was analysed by a different laboratory. Photographs of each site are given in Appendix 1.

Results

Ten variables were discarded from further investigation (Table 2). For some, only trace amounts had been measured. In other cases, there was no statistically significant difference between the samples.

A correlation matrix indicated that two pairs of the remaining analyses were highly correlated. To avoid distorting the analysis, only one of each was retained.

- Bicarbonate vs. Total Alkalinity ($r=0.999$): These are nearly identical in this dataset. Alkalinity was retained.
- E coli vs. Faecal Coliform Bacteria ($r=0.991$): These microbial indicators move almost perfectly in tandem. E coli was retained.

As an anion-cation balance serves more as a quality-control metric than a chemical indicator, it was also excluded from the matrix.

Eight variables were retained for further investigation (Table 3). Basic statistics of the variables, namely Minimum, Maximum, and Mean values for high-flow, low-flow, and overall samples, are given in Table 4. The IWUA sample was excluded from Table 4 calculations.

Exploratory multivariate analyses indicated that the P2 sample was generally out of step with the other 12 samples. Thus, this discussion focuses first on the eight-variable matrix of 12 samples. Principal components analysis (PCA) was performed on this matrix. Components 1 and 2 are plotted in Figure 2, and components 1 and 3 in Figure 3.

Variations in concentrations of the variables are usefully expressed in bar graphs. Four examples, shown in Figure 5, illustrate key PCA findings. In the graphs, samples are arranged in order from the river source to the exit for the Ntombe and Sibandlu Rivers, respectively.

Discussion

This is a very small sample on which to base concrete conclusions. There was always the possibility that a chance event at or immediately above a sampling point could distort the overall findings. Much more replication would be needed to reduce variability. Differences between the two river systems and time of year are small and subtle (Table 3). Element for element, the ranges of values are remarkably narrow.

- Chemical Stability: A pH range of 7.0 to 7.4 and Sodium ranging from 1 to 4 mg/L indicates a highly stable chemical environment. In many "peer" river systems (impacted by heavy industry or intensive agriculture), these values can fluctuate wildly.
- Health Assessment: Compared to many South African or global river systems, these rivers are in excellent health. With average Nitrate at 0.4 mg/L and E coli counts averaging around 42 (with many samples near zero), the water quality is far superior to that of rivers draining urban or industrial catchments. The "matrix" is sufficiently clean that multivariate analyses must work with very subtle differences to tease out trends.

The results, however, demonstrate how analysis can turn a "clean" and seemingly uniform dataset into a clear story of spatial, seasonal, and human-induced changes.

Principal components analysis

The first three components explain approximately 68.7% of the total variance in the laboratory data.

- **PC1 (28.7%) Figure 2:** Dominated by Electrical Conductivity (EC), pH and Total Dissolved Solids (TDS). This component reflects the overall mineralisation of the water, defined as the total quantity of dissolved inorganic salts (minerals) present. It is a measure of the "saltiness" or the ionic strength of the river system, excluding organic matter and suspended sediment. Samples L6 (known colloquially as Tweelingdam) and H1 (Langbossie) (low mineralisation) on the Sibandlu River were collected very close to where water bubbles up from the earth. Interestingly, these two samples are positioned close together at the positive end of PC1, even though they were collected during low- and high-flow periods, respectively, suggesting minimal change in mineralisation from heavy rainfall and runoff. H4 (Footbridge), H5 (Zendelingspos) and L5 (Concrete causeway), all from the Ntombe River, express intermediate mineralisation. All the other samples at the negative end of PC1, such as H2 (Diepkuil), H3 (Wandersheim), and L1 (Oosthuizenkrans), show a high degree of mineralisation. Although L1 is at the highest altitude of any sample, it has a relatively large catchment area, compared with the two other high-altitude samples, L6 and H1, which contribute to its high mineralisation score.

- **PC2 (21.1%) Figure 2:** Strongest contribution from Total Alkalinity and Nitrate. The gradient in Alkalinity strongly suggests dilution during the high-flow season (H4, H2, H6 and H3 on both rivers with low alkalinity, and corresponding high mineralisation on PC1). All low-flow samples are located at the negative end of PC2 (high Alkalinity).

Marked on PC2 is the extent of separation between the low- and high-flow samples from the same Node. Pairs of samples from the same site are shown connected by dotted lines. This indicates marked seasonal changes in chemical composition across sample sites, particularly at pairs H4-L4 (Ntombe) and H3-L3 (Sibandlu). This indicates that the variables driving PC2 exhibit pronounced seasonal variation across both rivers. In the dry season, low base flow increases Alkalinity across the entire study area. During the wet season, rainfall and runoff reduce Alkalinity.

- **PC3 (18.9%) Figure 3:** Primarily driven by positive E coli and Nitrate, and negative Sodium as Na. This captures the biological and nutrient-related variability. There is a clear separation on PC3 between the Ntombe system (high E coli and Nitrate on the positive end of PC3) and the Sibandlu system (low E coli and Nitrate on the negative end).

When looking at the principal component scores for the nodes where both High Flow (H) and Low Flow (L) samples were collected, there is a clear distinction in how the two river systems respond along the PC3 axis:

Node 1 H6-L5	Ntombe	0.15	Virtually no difference in response
Node 2 H4-L4	Ntombe	0.23	Minimal difference
Node 7 H2-L2	Sibandlu	0.46	Moderate shift
Node 8 H3-L3	Sibandlu	1.15	Marked shift

Ntombe Stability: The Ntombe nodes (1 and 2) show very low changes in "expression" on PC3. Since PC3 is primarily driven by E coli, Nitrate, and Sodium, this stability suggests that the sources of these parameters along the Ntombe are persistent and consistent, maintaining a similar chemical "fingerprint" regardless of the flow volume, potentially due to a stable, continuous source of loading.

Sibandlu Sensitivity: In contrast, the Sibandlu nodes (7 and 8) undergo significant shifts. Node 8, in particular, shows a shift (1.15) that is five to seven times greater than those seen on the Ntombe. This indicates that Sibandlu's water quality signature (specifically for biological and nutrient loads) is highly dynamic and changes fundamentally between seasons, suggesting its nutrient and microbial loads are more "intermittent" or flow-dependent than those of the Ntombe.

PC3 separates the Ntombe samples from the Sibandlu based on Nitrate and E coli. Because E coli and Nitrate are typical indicators of anthropogenic (human/livestock) impact, their dominance on the PC3 axis confirms that the Ntombe system is consistently more impacted/polluted than the Sibandlu system. One can conclude that the Ntombe system exhibits higher pollution than the Sibandlu system.

PCA, including P2: PCA was performed on the matrix including the IWUA sample. On PC1, the sample fitted in on the high mineralisation end, as expected of a sample where the river exits the study area. On PC2, the sample aggregated with most of the other high-flow samples (H4, H3, H2), although it was collected in May, a likely low-flow period. On PC3, this sample aggregated with low-flow Sibandlu samples (L1, L2, L3) exhibiting low pollution levels, while H5 at the same node had relatively high pollution indicators. In Table 2 (discarded analyses), the P2 sample shows deviations from the other samples, for example, in P-Alkalinity and Potassium as K levels. As the exact sampling procedure of P2 was unknown and it was analysed by a different laboratory, no further interpretation was attempted.

Bar charts

Bar charts were generated for key variables to illustrate the PCA findings.

TDS & Alkalinity (Figures 4a and 4b): These charts show the "Dilution Effect" discussed earlier. The Low-flow samples generally show higher mineralisation values than their corresponding High-flow counterparts at the same nodes (e.g., L2 vs H2). There is an increase in mineralisation from source to exit. H6 is an anomaly on the TDS chart.

E coli (Figure 4c): Clearly illustrates the difference in pollution loading between the Sibandlu River (low pollution) and the Ntombe River (high pollution)

Nitrate (Figure 4d): The Ntombe River (red bars) shows a distinctly higher baseline for Nitrate compared to the Sibandlu River (green bars), confirming the differential pollution profile mentioned in the PC3 analysis.

Conclusions

Although the sample was very small, with no replications at the same node at the same time of year, useful conclusions may be drawn.

The Upper Ntombe and Sibandlu systems are in an "excellent" state of health. Even at the exit nodes, Nitrate and E coli levels remain far below those found in urban or industrial South African catchments, validating the KPE's status as a critical hydrological asset.

The "dilution effect" is the dominant factor for mineral content. High-flow periods significantly reduce Total Alkalinity and TDS. However, "true" source nodes such as H1 and L6 exhibit remarkable chemical stability across both seasons, suggesting a highly pure groundwater origin with little initial runoff influence.

The study clearly distinguishes the two systems on the basis of human impact:

- Ntombe System: Displays a persistent pollution profile. The stability of PC3 scores across flow regimes suggests a continuous source of loading, likely linked to the irrigated fields and habitations in its upper reaches.

- Sibandlu System: Displays a highly dynamic profile. The significant seasonal shift at Node 8 indicates that its microbial and nutrient loads are intermittent and likely driven by specific runoff events rather than constant agricultural and anthropogenic discharge.

The heightened sensitivity of the Ntombe River to anthropogenic activity suggests that any future expansion of cultivation or livestock density in the KPE should be closely monitored to preserve its "flagship free-flowing" status.

Acknowledgements

Landowners are thanked for permission to collect samples on their properties.

Dr Johann Boonzaaier of the IWUA kindly provided the laboratory data for sample P2.

Horst Filter kindly provided long-term rainfall recordings for La Belle Esperance, a recording station within the KPE.

Statistical analyses were performed by Gemini 3, which also generated the graphics. Interpretation was by the author with inputs from Gemini 3.

References

MTPA (2014). Mpumalanga Biodiversity Sector Plan Handbook. Unpublished report, Mpumalanga Tourism and Parks Agency, Nelspruit, South Africa.

MTPA (2025). KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment Five-Year Management Plan:2025 – 2030. Unpublished report, Mpumalanga Tourism and Parks Agency, Nelspruit, South Africa.

Water Research Commission (2011). Atlas of Freshwater Ecosystem Priority Areas in South Africa. WRC Report No TT 500/11. ISBN: 978-1-4312-0146-4

Date saved: 2026-02-06

Figure 1. The upper reaches of the Ntombe (to the South) and Sibandlu (to the North) Rivers, tributaries of the Phongolo River, showing Nodes and samples. The confluence is at Node 9. The Eastern extent of the KPE is outlined in green.

Figure 2. Plot of PC1 against PC2. Green sample labels indicate the Sibandlu River, and red those from the Ntombe River. Dark symbols indicate low-flow samples and light symbols high-flow samples. Variable loading vectors are plotted in blue. Dotted lines join high- and low-flow samples from the same Node. Red arrows indicate trends discussed in the text.

Figure 3. Plot of PC1 against PC3. Green sample labels indicate the Sibandlu River, and red those from the Ntombe River. Dark symbols indicate low-flow samples and light symbols high-flow samples. Variable loading vectors are plotted in blue. Dotted lines join high- and low-flow samples from the same Node. Red arrows indicate trends discussed in the text.

Figure 4. Variation of values for a) TDS, b) Alkalinity, c) E coli and d) Nitrate across all samples, arranged from the river source to the exit from the study area. Green bars represent Sibandlu river samples and red bars Ntombe river samples. Dark shades indicate low-flow samples, and light shades indicate high-flow samples.

Table 1. Locations of samples according to Nodes. H1 to H6 at the time of high-flow and L1 to L6 at the time of low-flow. P2 (from IWUA) was sampled previously during low-flow.

Sample number	Node	Sample date	Lat/Long	Place and colloquial 'name'
H1	4	2026-01-05	30.514, -27.216	Sibandlu River, Groothoek/2, 'Langbossie'.
H2	7	2026-01-05	34.002, -31.503	Sibandlu River, Groothoek/2, Upstream of 'Diepkuil' drift.
H3	8	2026-01-05	34.053, -31.558	Sibandlu River, 'Wandersheim', Upstream of confluence with Nombe river.
H4	2	2026-01-05	34.032, -31.580	Ntombe River, Wandersheim, Upstream of turbine at 'Footbridge'.
H5	3	2026-01-05	30.698, -27.280	Ntombe River, Braunschweig Bridge, 'Zendelingspos'.
H6	1	2026-01-05	33.987, -31.548	Ntombe River, Roodewal, Upstream of concrete 'Causeway'.
L1	5	2025-06-19	33.952, -31.469	Sibandlu River, Groothoek/R, 'Oosthuizenkrans' stream. Upstream of drift.
L2	7	2025-06-20	34.002, -31.503	Sibandlu River, Groothoek/2, Upstream of 'Diepkuil' drift.
L3	8	2025-06-20	34.053, -31.558	Sibandlu River, 'Wandersheim', Upstream of confluence with Nombe river.
L4	2	2025-06-20	34.032, -31.580	Ntombe River, Wandersheim, Upstream of turbine at 'Footbridge'.
L5	1	2025-06-20	33.987, -31.548	Ntombe River, Roodewal, Upstream of concrete 'Causeway'.
L6	6	2025-06-20	33.983, -31.512	Sibandlu River, Groothoek/2, upstream of inlet to domestic water supply 'Tweelingdamme'.
P2	3	2022-05-23	30.698, -27.280	Ntombe River, Braunschweig Bridge, 'Zendelingspos'.
---	10			Confluence of Node 6 stream and Sibandlu River. No sample.
---	9			Confluence of Sibandlu and Ntombe Rivers. No sample.

Table 2. Discarded variables. All values are in standard analytical units.

SampleID	H1	H2	H3	H4	H5	H6	L1	L2	L3	L4	L5	L6	P2
Node	Node 4	Node 7	Node 8	Node 2	Node 3	Node 1	Node 5	Node 7	Node 8	Node 2	Node 1	Node 6	Node 3
Altitude (m)	1520	1420	1200	1240	1100	1340	1540	1420	1200	1240	1340	1500	1100
P-Alkalinity as CaCO ₃	<5	<5	<5	<5	<5	<5	<5	<5	<5	<5	<5	<5	17.1
Chloride as Cl	2	3	3	3	<2	<2	<2	<2	<2	2	2	<2	<6.00
Sulphate as SO ₄	<2	2	2	<2	<2	<2	2	2	2	<2	<2	<2	1.63
Ortho Phosphate as P	0.1	<0.1	0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	0.1	0.1	<0.1	<0.1	0.1	<0.1	<1.00
Free Cyanide as CN	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01
Potassium as K	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	1.21
Calcium as Ca	1	2	2	1	1	3	3	3	3	3	3	2	3.61
Magnesium as Mg	<1	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	1	1	<6.00
Manganese as Mn	<0.025	<0.025	<0.025	<0.025	<0.025	<0.025	<0.025	<0.025	<0.025	<0.025	<0.025	<0.025	0.024
Iron as Fe	<0.025	0.181	0.142	0.152	0.149	0.254	0.04	0.12	0.07	0.11	0.04	0.01	0.13

Table 3. Retained variables. Values exceeding the average are highlighted. All values are in standard analytical units.

SampleID	H1	H2	H3	H4	H5	H6	L1	L2	L3	L4	L5	L6	P2
Node	Node 4	Node 7	Node 8	Node 2	Node 3	Node 1	Node 5	Node 7	Node 8	Node 2	Node 1	Node 6	Node 3
Altitude (m)	1520	1420	1200	1240	1100	1340	1540	1420	1200	1240	1340	1500	1100
Sodium as Na	3.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	1.00	2.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	2.00	2.00	4.47
pH - Value @ 25 °C	7.00	7.40	7.40	7.30	7.30	7.10	7.20	7.30	7.20	7.20	7.20	7.10	7.31
Electrical Conductivity in mS/m @ 25°C	2.50	4.60	5.00	3.50	3.30	4.40	5.00	4.90	4.80	5.00	4.00	3.00	4.33
Total Dissolved Solids @ 180°C	22.00	36.00	34.00	30.00	34.00	48.00	36.00	36.00	40.00	34.00	28.00	26.00	29.00
Total Alkalinity as CaCO ₃	12.00	12.00	8.00	2.50	8.00	8.00	24.00	20.00	20.00	20.00	16.00	12.00	17.10
Nitrate as N	0.20	0.20	0.05	0.50	0.60	0.30	0.20	0.70	0.60	0.60	0.60	0.30	0.20
Chemical Oxygen Demand as O ₂ (Total)	16.00	12.00	16.00	12.00	16.00	20.00	16.00	12.00	5.00	20.00	5.00	5.00	5.00
E. coli	6.00	52.00	41.00	82.00	53.00	79.00	12.00	3.00	25.00	57.00	96.00	0.50	82.00

Table 4. Minimum, maximum, and average values for high-flow, low-flow, and overall variables (excluding P2). All values are in standard analytical units.

Variable	High Min	High Max	High Avg	Low Min	Low Max	Low Avg	All Min	All Max	All Avg
Sodium (as Na)	1.00	4.00	3.00	2.00	3.00	2.67	1.00	4.00	2.83
pH (at 25 °C)	7.00	7.40	7.25	7.10	7.30	7.2	7.00	7.40	7.23
Elec. Cond. (mS/m)	2.50	5.00	3.88	3.00	5.00	4.45	2.50	5.00	4.17
TDS (mg/L)	22.00	48.00	34.00	26.00	40.00	33.33	22.00	48.00	33.67
Alkalinity (as CaCO ₃)	2.50	12.00	8.42	12.00	24.00	18.67	2.50	24.00	13.54
Nitrate (as N)	0.05	0.60	0.31	0.20	0.70	0.5	0.05	0.70	0.40
COD (as O ₂)	12.00	20.00	15.33	5.00	20.00	10.5	5.00	20.00	12.92
E. coli	6.00	82.00	52.17	0.50	96.00	32.25	0.50	96.00	42.21

Appendix 1. Photographs of sample sites.

Node 5 Sample L1 (IMG_20250619_125625.jpg)

Node 7 Sample L2 (IMG_20250620_111511.jpg)

Node 8 Sample L3 (IMG_20250620_083155.jpg)

Node 2 Sample L4 (IMG_20250620_091451.jpg)

Node 1 Sample L5 (IMG_20250520_104253.jpg)

Node 6 Sample L6 (IMG_20250620_115359.jpg)

Node 4 Sample H1 (JWM26010413411.jpg)

Node 8 Sample H3 No photograph at this time of year. See Node 8 Sample L3 at the same location.

Node 7 Sample H2 (JWM26010506572.jpg)

Node 2 Sample (H4 JWM26010508052.jpg)

Node 3 Sample H5 (JWM20010510142.jpg)

Node 1 Sample H6 (JWM26010507301.jpg)